

Kinetics of Oxidation of Substituted Benzaldehydes by Potassium Permanganate in Acid Medium

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LITERATURE survey shows that Stewart¹ has studied the oxidation of aromatic aldehydes by KMnO_4 in buffer medium. It was also observed² that oxidation of substituted benzaldehydes by permanganate undergoes general acid catalysis. The observed results showed that the general acid catalysis was of the order pyrophosphate > dihydrogen phosphate > acetate. As an extension of the work, the oxidation of substituted benzaldehydes by KMnO_4 in H_2SO_4 medium, was made in order to study the various factors that affect the rate of reaction and also to propose a suitable mechanism.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were BDH (AnalaR) grade. Acetic acid was once refluxed over Chromium

trioxide and twice distilled over KMnO_4 . The middle fraction boiling at $117^\circ\text{--}118^\circ$ (literature value 118.5°) was used. An Elico pH meter Model LI-10 and Spekol colorimeter were used for determining pH and optical density respectively. The reaction was followed iodometrically as well as by colorimetric method due to disappearance of MnO_4^- at 527 nm.

Results and Discussion

The stoichiometry of the reaction was found to be 2 moles of MnO_4^- to 5 moles of $\text{X-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-CHO}$ and the product was identified as $\text{X-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-COOH}$. This can be explained by the following stoichiometric equation

The reaction was found to be first order in aldehyde and in permanganate respectively. The overall second order rate constant k_2 was calculated using the equation³. The rate constants were determined in $1\text{M H}_2\text{SO}_4$ in the temperature range between 15° to 30° and thermodynamic parameters are given in Table 1.

In aqueous acetic acid medium, rates were

TABLE 1
RATE CONSTANTS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS
[RCHO]₀ = $8.0 \times 10^{-4}\text{M}$; [KMnO_4]₀ = $4.0 \times 10^{-4}\text{M}$; Temperature = 25°C
 $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 = 1\text{M}$

Substituent	(Kl.m. ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹)					ΔE^\ddagger (K.cals/mole)	ΔH^\ddagger (K.cals/mole)	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ (e.u)
	15°	20°	25°	30°	35°			
<i>o</i> -NO ₂	0.54	3.77	1.05	1.44	1.93	11.4	10.8	22.2
<i>p</i> -CH ₃	0.40	0.56	0.77	1.25	1.86	12.33	11.7	19.8
-H	0.35	0.50	0.70	0.86	1.12	11.4	10.8	23.0
2, 6-Cl ₂	0.33	0.47	0.64	0.84	1.10	9.9	9.3	28.9
<i>o</i> -Cl	0.32	0.46	0.58	0.81	1.02	10.1	9.5	27.8
<i>p</i> -Cl	0.30	0.40	0.53	0.76	0.98	10.9	10.3	25.2
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	0.25	0.34	0.48	0.60	0.82	10.5	9.9	26.8
<i>m</i> -Cl	0.20	0.25	0.34	0.40	0.53	9.1	8.5	32.2
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	0.16	0.19	0.24	0.27	0.34	6.8	6.2	40.9

TABLE 2
SOLVENT EFFECT
[RCHO]₀ = $8.0 \times 10^{-4}\text{M}$; [MnO_4^-]₀ = $2.0 \times 10^{-4}\text{M}$
K(l.m.⁻¹ sec⁻¹)

Substituent	Temperature (°C)	Percentage of acetic acid V/V				
		10	20	30	40	50
<i>o</i> -NO ₂	32	0.43	0.47	0.60	1.28	2.50
<i>p</i> -CH ₃	32	0.25	0.42	0.50	0.93	1.40
-H	29	0.11	0.14	0.17	0.46	1.30
2, 6-Cl ₂	28	0.32	0.40	0.77	1.38	3.66
<i>o</i> -Cl	32	0.37	0.46	0.59	1.07	1.72
<i>p</i> -Cl	27	0.16	0.22	0.37	0.80	1.85
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	32	0.32	0.43	0.52	0.96	2.30
<i>m</i> -Cl	27	0.62	0.70	0.92	1.60	3.40
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	32	0.40	0.45	0.53	1.12	2.34

studied at different percentages of acid. The rate increased with decreasing dielectric constant suggesting that the reaction is of ion-dipole type. The rate constants for substituted benzaldehydes in acetic acid are given in Table 2.

The Hammett's plot for the oxidation of substituted benzaldehydes by KMnO_4 in $1\text{M H}_2\text{SO}_4$ at 25° gives a straight line with a slope $\rho = -0.70$. This shows that electron releasing substituents in the benzene ring accelerate the rate of reaction while electron withdrawing substituents retard the rate. This also indicates an electron deficient transition state. Since both meta and para substituents fit into the above plot, the resonance effect of the para substituent is probably small. However *p*-NO₂ compound deviates appreciably indicating a strong resonance interaction. It is also of interest

to discuss the effect of ortho-substituents on the reaction mechanism. Although the polar effects of ortho-substituents are generally recognised to be equal to those of para-substituents, the ortho-substituents in some case produce a large rate-enhancement as was observed by Vankatasubramanian⁴. Jayaraman⁵ while investigating the proximity and cumulative effect in the chromic acid oxidation of substituted benzaldehydes has observed the rate retardation with ortho-substituents because of steric hindrance. But our results using KMnO_4 as an oxidant indicates a reverse trend viz. $o\text{-NO}_2 > p\text{-NO}_2 > m\text{-NO}_2$ in nitro series and $2,6\text{-Cl}_2 > o\text{-Cl} > p\text{-Cl} > m\text{-Cl}$ in chloro series. This shows that steric hindrance is not of much importance. The plot of ΔH^\ddagger versus ΔS^\ddagger was linear with a slope equal to $\beta = 2401^\circ\text{K}$. This linear relationship indicates that all the substituted compounds studied follow the same type of mechanism. In order to find whether specific acid catalysis occurs, the experiments were conducted in concentrated H_2SO_4 and HClO_4 acid medium at different concentrations viz. 0.5 to 3.0M. The rate increases with increasing acid concentration and order with respect to H^+ is one upto 2.0 M. Bunnett's⁶ plot of $(\log k + \text{H}_0)$ versus $\log a_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ gave a straight line with slope 'w' equal to 6.5. Bunnett formulated that the 'w' values lying between 3.1 to 6.8, suggest a mechanism involving water molecule acting as a proton transfer agent. This can be explained by the following mechanism.

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New Mannich Bases from 5-(Methylphenoxy)methyl-1, 3, 4-oxadiazol 2-thione derivatives and their Bactericidal Properties

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THE herbicidal¹, bactericidal²⁻⁴ and insecticidal^{5,6} properties exhibited by oxadiazole compounds have made them of considerable interest specially in the field of pesticide chemistry. An effective insecticide based on oxadiazole moiety, against houseflies and cockroaches was patented⁷. Many Mannich bases have been reported to possess antibacterial⁸, fungicidal⁹ and anticonvulsant¹⁰ properties. In view of these observations a series of 3-arylamino-methyl-5-(methylphenoxy)methyl-1, 3, 4-oxadiazol 2-thione derivatives have been synthesised to study their bactericidal properties.

The key intermediates 5-methylphenoxy-methyl 1, 3, 4-oxadiazol-2-thiones prepared by the method of Young and Wood¹¹ were subjected to Mannich reaction according to procedure earlier reported in the literature^{12,13}.

The desired Mannich bases were isolated by two methods as described in the experimental.

The IR spectra of the Mannich bases showed the presence of C=S bands as sharp and strong peaks in the region of 1050-1090 cm^{-1} .

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Infra-red spectra were taken in a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer in KBr pellets.

5-(4-methylphenoxy)methyl-1, 3, 4-oxadiazol-2-thione (Ie)

A suspension of 0.1 mole of 4-methylphenoxy acetyl hydrazide, 0.1 mole of potassium hydroxide and 0.11 mole of carbon disulfide was refluxed on steam bath for 12 hours. The reaction mixture was cooled, solvent distilled off and residue dissolved in water and filtered. The clear filtrate was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and the separated solid was crystallised from ethanol to afford the compound (Ie). The other two compounds (Ia, Ic) were similarly prepared (analytical data vide Table 1).

3-Hydroxymethyl-5(4-methylphenoxy)methyl-1, 3, 4-oxadiazol-2-thione (If)

To a suspension of compound (Ie; 0.1 mole) in 100 ml ethanol was added formaldehyde (40%; 1.0 g). The reaction mixture was left overnight at room temperature, the separated solid was filtered and crystallised from ethanol to furnish compound (If). Two other compounds (Ib, Id) were prepared according to the same procedure (analytical data vide Table 1).